

TILSHUNOSLIKNING AMALIY MASALALARI: ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLARI, TARAQQIYOTI VA ISTIQBOLLARI

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

MATERIALLARI

2025-yil 29-30-sentabr

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**“TILSHUNOSLIKNING AMALIY MASALALARI:
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THE PLACE OF ACADEMIC BUOYANCY IN SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

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Introduction

Academic buoyancy, proposed by Martin and Marsh (2008) as part of a larger body of work, refers to learners' capacity to "bounce back" from the everyday challenges they inevitably encounter (Lakkavaara et al., 2024). These challenges may include stress of exams, tight deadlines, issues in peer and teacher relationships, and the ongoing task of sustaining motivation (Putwain et al., 2024). With its origins in Positive psychology, academic buoyancy adopts a proactive stance to deal with difficulties in educational circles. It takes into account a person's feelings, abilities, and skills to improve their psychological wellness (Jahedizadeh et al., 2019). Academic buoyancy is related to challenges that disturb motivation and engagement of learners by hurting their self-esteem and determination (Martin et al., 2017). However, motivation and engagement are not the only factors affecting academic buoyancy. It can also be affected by characteristics, confidence and motivation (Anderson et al., 2020). Learners with strong academic buoyancy tend to approach daily challenges, trusting in their ability to move past obstacles. They also maintain an optimistic outlook about achieving their learning objectives (Su & Wong, 2025). Furthermore, they are able to handle the frustration or boredom that can sometimes arise by viewing difficulties as a potential for development rather than as barriers they cannot overcome (Liu et al., 2022; Wang & Liu, 2022; Yun et al., 2018). Because of this mindset, these learners often make more consistent progress. They are able to stay motivated, develop genuine interest, strengthen their belief in their own abilities, and grow persistence (Putwain et al., 2023). In tough situations, this way of thinking helps them maintain their effort and curiosity, motivating them to

tackle problems directly and use proactive problem-solving mechanisms to keep moving forward (Su & Wong, 2025).

There is a plethora of studies on academic buoyancy in a wide range of academic disciplines. Previous research has shown that academic buoyancy supports student engagement and persistence (e.g., Malmberg et al., 2013), enhances psychological well-being (e.g., Martin et al., 2013; Miller et al., 2013), strengthens self-efficacy (e.g., Martin et al., 2010), contributes to academic achievement (e.g., Datu & Yang, 2021; Putwain et al., 2015; 2020), and is related to academic performance (e.g., Collie et al., 2024; Colmar et al., 2019; Guo et al., 2024; Putwain et al., 2016, 2024; Saalh & Kadhim, 2020).

Specifically, second language acquisition requires both persistence and resilience, making the concept of academic resilience particularly important. Effective second language learning depends on both motivation and on psychological characteristics that enable learners to surmount challenging situations (Fathi et al., 2025). Although learners' interest in language learning may fluctuate throughout the long and often demanding process, many remain committed to their goals despite obstacles. This determination is related to academic buoyancy (Yang et al., 2022). As an extension of motivation, resilience helps learners regulate daily fluctuations, sustain long-term effort, and recover from setbacks in their pursuit of L2 proficiency, thereby maintaining their motivation (Martin et al., 2010). Considering that second language acquisition is regarded as one of the most challenging and psychologically charging processes in the world (MacIntyre & Mercer, 2014), it is no surprise that academic buoyancy has emerged as a promising construct in second language acquisition research (Sudina & Plonsky, 2021). However, current evidence remains insufficient to provide a clear understanding of academic buoyancy in the EFL context (Alazemi et al., 2023). For this reason, this narrative review aims to synthesise existing literature, drawing primarily from Scopus and Web of Science, in order to clarify the potential place of academic buoyancy in SLA and highlight research gaps.

Methodology

This review has followed a narrative approach that focuses on conceptual scope rather than systematic coverage. Searches were conducted in Scopus and Web of Science databases using combinations of keywords: ("academic buoyancy") and ("second language acquisition" OR "language learning" OR "language teaching" or "foreign language learning"). The inclusion criteria selected for the articles were as follows:

1. They should be peer-reviewed journal articles.
2. They should be published in English.
3. They should address either academic buoyancy, resilience, or related affective constructs in SLA contexts.
4. They should be open-access publications.

Findings and Discussion

Across the studies reviewed, academic buoyancy has consistently been shown to yield positive effects in the EFL context. For instance, Xu and Wang (2022)

demonstrated that buoyancy can be closely attributed to learners' degree of motivation. Their findings suggest that once students feel motivated, they experience a sense of buoyancy toward their lessons, which in turn enhances their academic success and sustains their eagerness to learn. Similarly, Wang and Liu (2022) reported that academic buoyancy acts as a key mediator, enabling motivated language learners to stay engaged and resilient when confronted with the everyday challenges of EFL learning. Similar findings have also been reported by Aydın and Michou (2020), further reinforcing the link between buoyancy and motivation-driven persistence.

Another recurrent theme in the literature concerns the relationship between academic buoyancy and resilience. Yang et al. (2022) found that buoyancy gradually boosts language learners' persistence and enthusiasm, while Alazemi et al. (2023) emphasized its foundational role in both academic resilience and persistence by enabling learners to function effectively under challenging conditions. In line with this, Putwain et al. (2022, as cited in Zhou & Wang, 2024) observed that adaptability to challenges, which is manifested through enhanced positive reactions and diminished negative ones, is closely linked to academic buoyancy. Furthermore, Alazemi et al. (2023) suggested that buoyancy can both predict and mediate learners' regulation of academic emotions.

Building on these insights, Zhou and Wang (2024) observed that academic buoyancy reinforces the positive influence of enjoyable language learning while simultaneously mitigating the detrimental effects of burnout. Their findings indicate that higher levels of buoyancy not only protect students' test performance under increased burnout but also enhance the beneficial impact of enjoyment on achievement. In this sense, buoyancy provides valuable insight into the dynamic interplay between learners' emotions and their academic outcomes.

In the broader context of the disruptive obstacles and difficulties that are inherent to second language education (Li, 2023), buoyancy consistently emerges as a protective resource. It enables learners to sustain motivation and engagement even in the face of repeated setbacks and performance anxieties (Su & Wong, 2025). Finally, as Diert-Boté and Moncada-Comas (2024) argue, learners with high levels of buoyancy show confidence and high level of self-efficacy, particularly when speaking English. They also demonstrate effective task management and amply self-regulated learning strategies more successfully than their less buoyant peers

Conclusion

In conclusion, these findings suggest that academic buoyancy is not only a psychological resource but also a pedagogical priority in second language learning. It fosters motivation, enthusiasm, and self-efficacy among learners (Martin & Marsh, 2008), while simultaneously helps reduce negative emotions such as stress and lack of interest. Conversely, when learners have low academic buoyancy, they tend to experience difficulty concentrating, weakened attention, and reduced dedication to learning (Liu et al., 2024).

Given that foreign language learning is inherently filled with difficulties, ambiguities, and obstacles (Huang, 2022), it becomes essential for EFL teachers to

make sure that their students are supported psychologically so they can both enhance their proficiency and boost their buoyancy (Yang et al., 2022). By cultivating buoyancy, researchers and teachers also can deepen their awareness of learner psychology and design more effective instructional practices that sustain students' motivation and engagement in language acquisition.

While research on resilience has provided an important foundation, academic buoyancy remains relatively underexplored in SLA and needs further empirical investigation (Ibrahim & Basim, 2024). Future studies should aim to develop context-specific measures, explore cultural variations, and examine how buoyancy interacts with other affective factors to shape successful language learning.

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TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISHDA KOMPETENTSIYALI YONDASHUVNING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada o'quvchi-yoshlar ongiga ijobiy fazilatlar, ma'naviy qadriyatlarni singdirishda adabiyot o'qituvchisining kompetentsiyaviy yondashuvi, shuningdek, badiiy asarlarni o'rgatishda innovatsion ta'lim muhitini yaratish, uni xalqaro andozalarga to'liq mosligini ta'minlash bugungi kunning eng dolzarb muammolaridan biri ekahligi tahlil etilgan.

Tayanch so'zlar: Ma'naviyat, qadriyat, badiiy adabiyot, ta'lim va tarbiya, kompetentsiyaviy yondashuv, innovatsiya, davlat ta'lim standarti, zamonaviy texnologiy, media vositalar.

Abstract. In the article, the competent approach of the literature teacher in instilling positive qualities, spiritual values in the minds of students and young people, as well as creating an innovative educational environment in teaching works of art, ensuring its full compliance with international standards, is analyzed as one of the problems of today's world.

Key words: Spirituality, value, fiction, education and upbringing, competence approach, innovation, state education standard, modern technology, media tools.

O'zbekiston Respublikasida dunyoning rivojlangan mamlakatlari kabi kompyuter va axborot texnologiyalarini rivojlantirishga yanada e'tibor berilib, o'quv dasturlari va o'quv fanlari bo'yicha DTS kompetentsiyali yondashuv asosida qayta ishlandi.

Mazkur kompetentsiyali yondashuv asosida shakllantirilgan DTS amaliyotga joriy etish ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonining boshqa tarkibiy qismlari: o'qitish metodlari, vositalari va shakllariga innovatsiya kiritish orqali modernizatsiyalashni talab etadi.